

DIGITAL INNOVATION IN WASTE COLLECTION AND RECYCLING

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Abstract:

In municipal governance around the world, the use of collective intelligence methods with dedicated tools, mobile apps and platforms is becoming the norm as a way to involve citizens, users and stakeholders in the design and implementation of policies. Artificial Intelligence can also help fact check information and help generate automatic summaries and map concepts. Location information plays an essential role in the far majority of Digital Platforms and the importance of location intelligence is reaching new heights thanks to the more than 25 billion devices that will be connected to the “Internet of Things” (IoT) by 2021. Safe and cost-effective management of municipal solid waste is a significant social, environmental and health challenge for modern society. The waste sorting includes many tasks with “three D’s” (dirty, dull and dangerous) that are typical targets of work that would be better done by a machine. A robot needs highly sophisticated visual and manipulation skills to be able to work on the extremely heterogeneous and complex waste environment. These skills were not available until AI and advanced robotics disruption occurred in recent years. With the help of AI, future waste treatment plants as very automatized and optimized facilities where no human will be in direct contact with waste, and where almost all recyclables will be recovered, no more going to incineration or landfills. This article discuss about need of Digitalization in waste management and its importance.

Keywords – Digitalization, waste, intelligence, technology, management

INTRODUCTION

The waste management and recycling industry is not very enthusiastic about its progress in adapting to new technologies. According to a study, about 60 percent of waste management and recycling professionals gave themselves a failing grade for the application of new technologies. Also, most companies gave themselves a grade of “unsatisfactory” in these areas. Yet about 64 percent of those surveyed expect an increase in their information technology (IT) budgets, with 20 percent expecting an increase to their IT budgets of more than 5 percent. According to a study, more than 80 percent of participants regardless of whether they are municipalities or private sector waste management companies believe that

digital innovation is important for their business success. At the top of their priorities list is improving customer satisfaction (73 percent) and increasing productivity (72 percent). Additionally, more than half of respondents (52 percent) indicated that improving sustainability is a big priority. Yet to achieve this, that the most important issue for management is how to organize the operational process in terms of both harmonization and digitalization. The main barriers include obsolete legacy IT systems, implementing a paperless organization and creating a culture open to change.

Digital Platforms enable multi-directional network effects and value creation and allow platform owners - managers to address the markets. The near-zero marginal cost curve of Digital Platforms create the possibility of market domination by one platform and the high barriers to entry or exit lead to monopolistic and oligopolistic market structures. On the other side Developing Digital Platform businesses requires a shift in design thinking from resource ownership to resource orchestration. Several recommendations have been developed by EU for how Digital Platforms could more easily apply and expand in the context of government environments. The main ones concern that governments should focus on orchestrating and reusing existing government services as a starting point for developing their Digital Platforms, they should start building IoT capabilities and optimize the use of their open data services by defining a service delivery approach that matches the needs of their target consumers OECD has recommended “that governments develop and implement digital government strategies” to assist and guide them to achieve that digital transformation.

The Recommendation emphasizes the crucial contribution of digital technologies as a strategic driver to create open, participatory and trustworthy public sectors, to improve social inclusiveness and government accountability, and to bring together government and non-government actors and develop innovative approaches to contribute to national development and long-term sustainable growth. The greatest challenge of collective intelligence lies in engaging citizen. It is extremely difficult to mobilize a large range of the population that has a diversified base of knowledge on specific public policy issue. This is compounded by the challenge of finding the right balance of key stakeholders and citizens to provide political legitimacy to the consultation. The application of EPR and other recycling schemes, their supervision and monitoring is becoming easier through the Digitalization of the waste sector. Tracing hazardous materials and substances, restricting illegal treatment and disposal and

preventing waste trafficking is also advanced due to digital footprints, IoT and modern surveillance techniques. Waste collection and source separation recycling programs are already digitized in many cities while important private and public sector operators are preparing their digitalization strategies.

Benefits of Digitalization of waste collection and recycling programs

- ✓ Cost and resource recovery optimization
- ✓ Full control of the operations and their efficiency
- ✓ A better understanding of the spatial and temporal patterns of waste generation and storage and in depth profiling of the users' behavior
- ✓ Higher flexibility, easy adaptation of the services to changing patterns and targeted interventions
- ✓ The rise of on demand services and tailor made services
- ✓ Easier and faster application of Pay as You Throw Systems
- ✓ Important user / provider interfaces (through mobile apps & web platforms) that allow direct complain management and easy identification of problematic points.

Semi-driverless waste collection vehicles have already been tested with good results. Their commercialization will deliver substantial benefits in operational costs, endless optimization opportunities, better safety and less occupational risks. Advances in Robotics, Advances in neurosciences and brain studies allowed researchers to simulate natural language processing and programming in a way the improved substantial, the contextual understanding of robots in narrowly defined contexts. Contextual Understanding, Advances in computing power and cloud robotics allow the development of algorithms that teach robots to adapt continuously to specified dynamic environments Situational.

The Rise of Robots & Automation in Waste Treatment

Robotic waste sorting systems are autonomous, multitasking, learning and scalable systems that can operate tirelessly 24/7. Robotic systems capable to separate specific materials are already commercially available for different waste streams. Their accuracy varies depending on the type of recognition methods they use and the target materials but it is continuously improved. Till now, the experiences gained demonstrate that the robotic

recycling revolution is driven most importantly by significant cost savings generated by process efficiency, and improved revenue streams from high-purity recyclables that are now more diverse, thanks to unique recognition capabilities made possible by artificial intelligence.

In brief, the impact of robotic recycling in treatment facilities involves:

- Reduced reliance on manual sorters – the main trend is to increase the working distance between the actual handling of materials and human beings and reduce the relevant occupational health and safety problems. Thus, it's not that treatment facilities will run without workers but that workers will have to work in close cooperation with intelligent robots that will do all the dirty work.
- More flexible sorting lines – merging visual data with sensors and big data analytics, robotic sorting lines create opportunities for operational benefits that were never imagined before like direct identification of where, when and how many losses in materials occur or real-time data about what is recovered and quick adjustments based on daily or weekly targets.
- Better knowledge of the waste input - using the information provided by sensors and visual recognition, operators are now able to understand the input waste composition in depth, to easily predict daily and seasonal effects and automatically adjust the lines in the expected inputs.
- Market adaptation - As the revenues relevant to recycling are depending on market prices and conditions, a core function of resource recovery facilities is to advance the recovery of materials that are priced higher and reduce the recovery of low-value materials. According experienced operators in robotics, such adjustments will gradually become completely automatic and the robotic operations will be guided by market prices inputs to their software and algorithms. It is stressed that till now robotic systems are used to optimize specific material separation activities. But as robotics is becoming better and gradually they will be the mainstream for material separation, a completely new design of facilities is expected to appear within the next 3-5 years. This design will have the robots at the center of the operations and humans in a more supervisory role, probably in distance from the waste streams.

Five digital transformation trends were identified to create new opportunities within the waste recycling industry:

- Use of waste data tracking includes RFID technology and fills sensors to detect fill levels and monitor all the materials generated, reused, and recycled.
- Development and adoption of digital solutions such as smart bins, smart trucks, robotic sorting, mobile applications, and analytical tools as well as optimization software
- Implementation of key innovative business models such as freemium (a pricing strategy by which a product or service is provided free of charge, but money is charged for additional features or services) and Everything-as-a-Service (XaaS).
- Focus on customer experience (CX) to build strong relationships with companies and end users.
- Adoption of crowdsourcing and customization to boost demand for big data analytics and cloud computing.

The New Role of Labour

Several studies estimate huge job losses due to the on-going automation wave. A recent report by the World Economic Forum suggested that while robots will displace 75 million jobs globally in the next 10 years, 133 million new jobs could be created because of automation. Similarly, the McKinsey Global Institute reckons that although between 400 and 800 million jobs are at risk, advances in AI and automation could transform our working lives, creating new roles and freeing people up to fill them. It is clear that in waste treatment facilities and in landfills, and probably to a lesser extent in waste collection, the rise of robots will alter fundamentally the role of the labor. However, there is a need for a closer examination of what the expected changes will be. Overall, someone can categorize the expected changes in employment related to the following three waves:

- Algorithm wave: focused on automation of simple computational tasks and analysis of structured data in areas like finance, information and communications – this is already well underway in consulting firms and administrative structures related to waste management.

- Augmentation wave: focused on automation of repeatable tasks through dynamic technological support, and statistical analysis of unstructured data in semi-controlled environments such as aerial drones for landfills.
- Autonomy wave: focused on automation of physical labour and manual dexterity, and problem solving in dynamic real-world situations that require responsive actions, such as in manufacturing and transport (e.g. driverless waste collection vehicles) – these technologies are under development already, but may only come to full maturity on an economy-wide scale in the 2030s.

Finally, it must be clear that the introduction of robots creates also serious changes to the working relationships. A recent study by the US National Bureau of Economic Research found that each new robot added to the workforce meant the loss of between 3 and 5.6 jobs in the local commuting area. Meanwhile, for each new robot added per 1,000 workers, wages in the surrounding area would fall between 0.25 and 0.5 percent. It's also important to remember that these job and wage losses are not distributed evenly among the population. Some jobs are expectedly more fragile than others. The major categories experiencing substantial declines are routine manual occupations, blue-collar workers, operators and assembly workers, and machinists and transport workers. The only jobs not affected were managerial ones.

Indian Scenario

Management of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is integral to improve sanitation condition and living quality of 377 million people (31% of total population) living in urban India. The MSW sector will add another 100 million tonnes of waste in next 13 years on the pretext of growing urban population (migration), changing lifestyles and changing consumption patterns (10). Of 62 million tons of MSW generated annually, only 15-20 % gets treated and rest lands up in dumpsites, landfills or open lands burdening vast expense of limited and costly land resources and contaminating the environment. Despite this situation, the Waste sector is seldom recognised as an essential utility service underpinning modern society compared to other services in India. Some key challenges in MSW sector are:

- Lack of interdepartmental (water, waste & energy) cooperation (synergy) within government (ULBs)
- Lack of incentive for source segregation
- Lack of infrastructure and the poorly developed market for recycling and resource recovery
- Inadequate technical & managerial expertise in the waste sector (formal training or hands-on practice)
- The absence of linkage between science (academics & research) and practice (industries and public organisations) >lack of translational research.

Key opportunities exist in India are:

- ❖ Existence of an informal recycling industry
- ❖ Strong presence of Information Technology (IT) industry
- ❖ Youth dividend (average population age-29 years by 2020)
- ❖ Increasing political support for waste management
- ❖ Collaboration bet. India & Germany for vocational education and sustainable development goals
- ❖ Availability of International climate finance for achieving global climate protection targets

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